

Targeted-lung delivery of dexamethasone using gated mesoporous silica nanoparticles. A new therapeutic approach for acute lung injury treatment

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ABSTRACT

Acute lung injury (ALI) is a critical inflammatory syndrome, characterized by increased diffuse inflammation and severe lung damage, which represents a clinical concern due to the high morbidity and mortality in critical patients. In last years, there has been a need to develop more effective treatments for ALI, and targeted drug delivery to inflamed lungs has become an attractive research field. Here, we present a nanodevice based on mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with dexamethasone (a glucocorticoid extensively used for ALI treatment) and capped with a peptide that

targets the TNFR1 receptor expressed in pro-inflammatory macrophages (**TNFR-Dex-MSNs**) and avoids cargo leakage. **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanoparticles are preferentially internalized by pro-inflammatory macrophages, which overexpressed the TNFR1 receptor, with the subsequent cargo release upon the enzymatic hydrolysis of the capping peptide in lysosomes. Moreover, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** are able to reduce the levels of TNF- α and IL-1 β cytokines in activated pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages. The anti-inflammatory effect of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** is also tested in an *in vivo* ALI mice model. The administered nanodevice (intravenously by tail vein injection) accumulated in the injured lungs and the controlled dexamethasone release reduces markedly the inflammatory response (TNF- α IL-6 and IL-1 β levels). The attenuation in lung damage, after treatment with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, is also confirmed by histopathological studies. Besides, the targeted-lung dexamethasone delivery results in a decrease of dexamethasone derived side-effects, suggesting that targeted nanoparticles can be used for therapy in ALI and could help to overcome the clinical limitations of current treatments.

KEYWORDS

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles; Gated nanodevices; TNFR peptide; Dexamethasone delivery; ALI treatment

1. INTRODUCTION

Acute lung injury (ALI), with its more severe form of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS), is a severe inflammatory disease, main cause of morbidity and mortality in critical patients in which acute diffuse inflammation develops as well as alterations in lung function and structure, resulting in many cases in a severe respiratory failure [1,2]. ALI is characterized, especially in the early stages, for an increase in lung permeability leading to interstitial and alveolar edema with the subsequent formation and accumulation of alveolar hyaline membranes [3,4]. The inflammatory response is also activated and multiple inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α ,

IL-6, IL-1 β , etc.) are released in concert with neutrophil influx to the alveolar space of the injured lung [5,6]. The advances in the understanding of the pathophysiology of ALI have led to the development of numerous pharmacological treatments [7]. However, clinical trials revealed that these are not as effective as expected, mainly limited to the difficulty of the drugs to reach the injured lungs [8,9]. Thus, there is a real interest in the development of more effective treatments for ALI and the preparation of systems for the direct delivery of drugs in the lung has become an active research area [10,11].

In this scenario, several nanotechnological-based strategies to specifically deliver drugs in lungs based on the use of lipids, organic polymers, nanogels, and inorganic nanoparticles have been developed in the last years [12–15]. Among nanoparticles, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are excellent candidates as a scaffold for drug storage and on-command delivery due to the possibility of decorating their external surface with (supra)molecular or biomolecular gating ensembles (also known as nanovalves or gatekeepers), which controlled cargo release upon application of external stimuli [16–19]. This is a clear advantage when compared with nanodevices constructed using liposomes and polymeric carriers, which usually release their cargo by carrier-degradation or diffusion-controlled processes [20–22]. Besides, MSNs also possess several remarkable features such as high surface area, homogenous and tuneable pore size, easy functionalization, good biocompatibility, prolonged retention time, and physiological stability [23–26]. In fact, gated MSNs have been successfully used in several applications, and their capability to improve the availability and pharmacokinetics of encapsulated drugs, reducing undesired side effects, has been demonstrated in *in vivo* models [27–31].

Regarding ALI, MSNs could be suitable nanocarriers to direct drug delivery for the treatment of ALI due to their preferential accumulation on the lungs as well as to inflamed tissue [32–34]. It has been widely demonstrated that the vascular nature, high permeability, and retention capacity of the lungs facilitate the preferential accumulation

of MSNs [35–39]. This preferential accumulation is ascribed to a passive targeting mechanism called ELVIS (Extravasation through Leaky Vasculature and Inflammatory cell-mediated Sequestration) that can be exploited for the treatment of inflammatory diseases [40,41]. In addition to passive targeting, an active targeting strategy can also be used to make the nanoparticles more specific to the target site. Concerning ALI, one common approach is to target the inflamed endothelium in the lungs. In this scenario, some studies described the use of lipid carriers or polymers modified with antibodies to target the pulmonary vascular-endothelium by binding ICAM (intercellular adhesion molecule 1) receptor [42–44]. Moreover, some recent approaches to deal with ALI have focused on the use of antibodies, in the absence of nanoparticles, against the CD64 (Fc γ receptor I) or tumour necrosis factor receptor (TNFR) which are overexpressed in pro-inflammatory macrophages [45–48].

On the other hand, glucocorticosteroids (GCs), as strong anti-inflammatory drugs, are widely used to ameliorate ALI clinical symptoms by limiting tissue injury and acute inflammatory response [49,50]. Among GCs, dexamethasone (Dex) is one of the most used for ALI treatment and its administration induces a decrease of the pro-inflammatory cytokines, a reversal in lung tissue injury, and a reduction in pulmonary edema [51,52]. However, despite the potential therapeutic effect of Dex and the improvement of ALI outcome, its use remains a serious concern due to its undesired side-effects attributed to its broad spectrum of action [53,54]. In order to overcome these drawbacks, efficient GCs delivery strategies using appropriate vehicles have been described in numerous inflammatory diseases [55–57]. However, focusing in the treatment of ALI, only two reports described the encapsulation of Dex and efficient lung delivery in an acute lung injury model using lipid nanocarriers [58,59].

Based on the above, we report herein the preparation of a lung-targeted drug delivery nanodevice for the treatment of ALI. The nanodevice consists of MSNs loaded with rhodamine B (RhB) or Dex and capped with a peptide containing the binding sequence

to the tumour necrosis factor receptor 1 (TNFR1) [60] which is expressed in pro-inflammatory macrophages and is involved in the progress of the inflammatory response. The nanodevice is designed to take advantage of the MSNs intrinsic passive targeting to inflammation and lungs in combination with an active targeting to TNFR. Here, we demonstrate the activity of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanodevice *in vitro* in inflammatory macrophages and *in vivo* in an ALI mice model, confirming lung targeting high anti-inflammatory effects while minimizing undesired side effects. The results exhibited the potential of using MSNs for the development of new therapeutic strategies for ALI as well as other respiratory diseases. While different nanomaterials have been developed for GCs encapsulation and ALI treatment independently, only a few nanocarriers have been used for GCs delivery in ALI. Moreover, and as far as we know, our report herein describes the first use of MSNs as a drug delivery system in an acute lung injury model.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Design, synthesis, and characterization of TNFR-gated nanodevices

For the synthesis of the TNFR-gated nanodevices, MSNs were selected as an inorganic scaffold. The pores were loaded with rhodamine B or dexamethasone and the external surface functionalized with isocyanatopropyl moieties (solids **NCO-RhB-MSNs** and **NCO-Dex-MSNs**, respectively). Then, the TNFR1 peptide (GGGGFIGLMYRYQRWKSPLY) was anchored onto the external surface of the silica nanoparticles, through the formation of urea bonds, yielding the **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanoparticles. An illustration showing the structure of the nanodevices is depicted in Scheme 1A. The nanoparticles are expected to reach the inflamed lungs in acute lung injury (ALI) mice models with the subsequent uptake by pro-inflammatory macrophages through a TNFR1 mediated endocytosis, and to deliver the cargo (dexamethasone) due to degradation of the capping ensemble in the endocytic compartment (Scheme 1B). Besides, to evaluate the targeting ability of the

TNFR1 peptide-functionalized nanoparticles, similar nanodevices loaded with rhodamine B or dexamethasone but capped with a random peptide sequence (i.e. KKRSFLGSELLVGAVTMGTLFWRKK), unable to bind with TNFR1 receptor, were also prepared (**Random-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-Dex-MSNs**, respectively).

Scheme 1. Design of the TNFR-MSNs nanodevices for acute lung injury therapy.

A) Representation of the designed TNFR-gated nanodevices. MSNs were loaded with rhodamine B or with dexamethasone, functionalized with (3-isocyanatopropyl)triethoxysilane, and capped with a peptide that recognized TNFR1 in macrophages. B) Schematic illustration of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** in vivo application in ALI mouse model. After intravenous (i.v.) injection of the nanoparticles in mice, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** preferentially reached the inflamed lungs and TNFR1 mediated endocytosis of the nanodevices in pro-inflammatory macrophages with the subsequent controlled drug delivery.

The prepared nanoparticles were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), TEM, N₂ adsorption-desorption curves, dynamic light scattering, and zeta potential. The PXRD patterns of the starting MSNs showed low angle reflections typical of mesoporous materials with a hexagonal order (Figure S1) which is preserved in the nanoparticles **NCO-RhB-MSNs**, **NCO-Dex-MSNs**, **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**. TEM images of the starting MSNs (Figure 1A) show the nanoparticles as spheres of ca. 100 nm and the mesopores as alternate black and white channels. The same morphology was also observed in the final and intermediate solids. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms of the starting MSNs showed a type IV isotherm, typical of the mesoporous silica materials, with a BET specific surface area of 1167 m²/g, 0.96 cm³/g of pore volume and pore size of 2.5 nm. In contrast, N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm of the final nanodevices **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** was typical of mesoporous systems with partially filled mesopores with reduced specific surface areas (Table 2 and Figure S2).

The different preparation steps were also monitored by dynamic light scattering (DLS). The hydrodynamic diameter increased after each preparation step, starting from 103 ± 25 nm for **MSNs** to a final size of 194 ± 18 and 222 ± 17 nm for **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, respectively (Figure 1B). In the case of **Random-RhB-MSNs** (179 ± 34 nm) and **Random-Dex-MSNs** (230 ± 18 nm) similar values were obtained (see also Figure S3). A single population distribution was observed for all nanoparticles suggesting the particles were not aggregated, even after the loading and capping process with the targeting peptide. Besides, zeta potential changed from the characteristic negative value of bare **MSNs** (-32 ± 3 mV) to positive values after the cargo and functionalization process (17 ± 2 mV and 19 ± 1 mV for **NCO-RhB-MSNs** and **NCO-Dex-MSNs**). The final **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** solids also presented a positive zeta potential of 8 ± 1 mV and 7 ± 1 mV, respectively, due to the presence of the positively charged peptide attached to the external surface of the

nanoparticles (Figure 1C). Similarly, the values for the solids **Random-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-Dex-MSNs** were also positive, with a zeta potential of 5 ± 1 and 13 ± 2 mV respectively (Figure S3). The amounts of Dex ($340 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg SiO}_2$, $0.86 \text{ mmol}/\text{g SiO}_2$) and TNFR peptide ($0.05 \text{ mmol}/\text{g SiO}_2$) in **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** solid were determined by thermogravimetric and HPLC studies. The same techniques were used to determine rhodamine B ($0.16 \text{ mmol}/\text{g SiO}_2$) and TNFR peptide ($0.04 \text{ mmol}/\text{g SiO}_2$) in **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**. Finally, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanoparticles showed a signal at 163.5 eV which corresponds to S2p and thus to the TNFR peptide which contain a methionine residue (Figure S4). Besides, this signal was absent in the XPS spectra of **NCO-Dex-MSNs** (Figure S4).

Figure 1. TNFR-gated nanoparticles characterization. A) Representative images from TEM from **MSNs**, **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**; B) Hydrodynamic size distribution determined by dynamic light scattering; C) Zeta potential for the different prepared materials; D) Schematic illustration of TNFR1 mediated endocytosis of the nanoparticles and subsequent controlled drug delivery in pro-inflammatory macrophages; E) Release profiles of rhodamine B from **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** in PBS at pH 7.4 and in presence of lysosomal extract at pH 5.0-6.0; F) Dexamethasone release from **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** in PBS at pH 7.4, PBS at pH 5.5, and in the presence of lysosomal extract. Data of each figure represent the means \pm SD of at least three independent experiments.

To study the gating ability of the capping peptide, payload delivery from **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** was studied in PBS at pH 7.4 (mimicking physiological conditions) and in lysosomal extract at mildly acidic conditions (pH in the 5.0-6.0 range) simulating the endocytic cellular compartment (Figure 1D). PBS suspension of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** at pH 7.4 showed negligible rhodamine B release (Figure 1E). However, a marked delivery was observed when the nanodevice was suspended in lysosomal extract reaching ca. 80% of the maximum rhodamine B delivery after 60 min. The observed release is attributed to the action of lysosomal enzymes that hydrolysed the TNFR capping peptide. Besides, the controlled release of dexamethasone from **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** was also studied in PBS at pH 7.4, PBS at pH 5.5 and in the presence of lysosomal extract. The obtained results are shown in Figure 1F. In PBS at both pH tested (5.5 and 7.4) a nearly zero dexamethasone release was observed, whereas a marked payload release was found (ca. 90% of the maximum drug delivery after 60 min) in the presence of lysosomal extract, attributed to the hydrolysis of TNFR peptide.

2.2. TNFR-gated MSNs preferentially deliver its cargo in pro-inflammatory macrophages.

In a first step, the biocompatibility of the nanodevices was assessed in immune cells and epithelial lung cells. Cell viability studies in the presence of TNFR-gated nanomaterials at different concentrations were performed in THP-1 monocytes and A549 epithelial lung cells (Figures 2A and 2B). After 24 h of treatment cell viability was kept in all cases up to 80% even at the highest **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** concentrations (100 µg/mL). A study of the release of the intracellular lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) enzyme to the extracellular media, as an inflammatory cell death marker, in both THP-1 monocytes and A549 epithelial lung cells treated with the nanoparticles, demonstrated that **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** were unable to induce inflammatory cell death in these cells (Figures 2A and 2B). In parallel, cell viability and LDH release assays were also performed with the other prepared materials (bare MSNs, **NCO-RhB-MSNs**, **NCO-Dex-MSNs**, **Random-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-Dex-MSNs**) yet any sign of nanoparticle-associated toxicity was observed (Figure S5). The results suggested the suitability of the TNFR-nanodevice for further implementation in lung therapy, showing no obvious toxicity effects towards immune cells as well as epithelial lung cells.

The cellular uptake and trafficking of TNFR-gated MSNs were also evaluated in pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages. As TEM images revealed (Figure 2C and Figure S8), **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** were internalized by pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages through the endocytosis pathway after 1h of nanoparticle incubation (Figure 2C, left). The process involves the formation of endocytic vesicles able to fuse with endosomes. Finally, the ingested nanoparticles were transferred into lysosomes in which remained until their degradation (Figure 2C, right). Besides, these results were corroborated by confocal microscopy assays in which it was observed that rhodamine-labelled TNFR-MSNs (**TNFR-RhB*-MSNs**) were poorly internalized when cells were previously incubated

with the endocytic inhibitor dynasore (Figure S7). Moreover, in the absence of dynasore a clear colocalization between the fluorescence signal of the nanoparticles and lysotracker confirmed the entrapment of the nanoparticles into the lysosomes. These results confirmed the endocytic uptake of TNFR-gated MSNs.

As stated above, the nanoparticles are capped with a peptide designed to target the TNFR1 receptor in inflammatory cells. The TNFR1 receptor is expressed both in THP-1 monocytes and overexpressed in pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages (Figure 2D). Cellular uptake of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** in THP-1 monocytes (Figure S9) and pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages was studied by flow cytometry (Figure 2E) and confocal microscopy (Figure 2F). Besides, to demonstrate the targeting ability of the capping peptide in **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, internalization studies were performed with the nanoparticles capped with a random peptide (**Random-RhB-MSNs**). Flow cytometry experiments confirmed the preferential internalization of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** in inflammatory cells when compared with the uptake of **Random-RhB-MSNs** (Figure 2E). In addition, confocal microscopy images revealed a clear increase in rhodamine B fluorescence signal inside pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages (Figure 2F) after 4 h of treatment with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, while lower intensity of fluorescence was observed with **Random-RhB-MSNs**. These results demonstrate the targeting ability of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** to inflammatory M1 macrophages due to the selective interaction between the capping TNFR peptide and the TNFR1 receptor in the cell membrane.

Figure 2. TNFR-gated nanoparticles biocompatibility and targeted cellular uptake. A) Cell viability and LDH release in THP-1 cells at different concentrations (0, 25, 50 and 100 µg/mL) of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** (light pink) and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** (light grey) at 24 h. **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** treatments correspond to 0, 12.5, 25 and 50 µM of dexamethasone, respectively. B) A549 cell viability and LDH release at 24 h in the presence of different **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** (light pink) and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** (light grey) dosages. P represents the positive control of lysate cells. Data represent the means ± SEM of at least three independent experiments. C) TEM images showing **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** internalization in pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages after 1 and 4 h of

incubation. D) Western blot analysis of TNFR1 expression in the different inflammatory cells; monocytes THP-1, non-differentiated M0 macrophages and pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages. E) Fluorescence intensity of pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages analysed by flow cytometry after **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** or **Random-RhB-MSNs** treatment for 1 and 4 h. Data expressed as mean \pm SEM by statistical significance determined using a two-way ANOVA (**p <0.001). F) Confocal images of nanoparticle uptake in pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages in the presence of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** or **Random-RhB-MSNs** after 4 h. Rhodamine B associated fluorescence in red and DNA Hoechst 33342 in blue.

2.3. TNFR-Dex-MSNs efficiently reduce inflammatory response in activated macrophages.

Once assessed the targeting ability of the nanodevices, we tested the use of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** to modulate the inflammatory response. Dexamethasone is a potent immunosuppressant that reduces the release of TNF- α [61] and IL-1 β [62]. To analyze the anti-inflammatory activity of the nanodevices, the NLPR3 inflammasome was activated in pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages by treatment with lipopolysaccharide LPS and nigericin (NG). This treatment produces the release of the pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-1 β . Under these conditions, M1 macrophages were treated with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** (as control, 2 μ g/mL), **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** (2 μ g/mL, equivalent to 1 μ M of dexamethasone), and free dexamethasone (1 μ M) and the levels of IL-1 β and TNF- α measured by ELISA. Besides, **Random-RhB-MSNs** (as control, 2 μ g/mL) and **Random-Dex-MSNs** (2 μ g/mL, equivalent to 1 μ M of dexamethasone) were used to compare the targeted efficacy of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**. A marked and similar reduction in IL-1 β and TNF- α levels were found when activated pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages were treated with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** and free dexamethasone (Figure 3A

and 3B) while as expected no changes were observed upon treatment with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**. Besides, lower decreases of IL-1 β and TNF- α levels were achieved using **Random-Dex-MSNs** at equivalent Dex concentrations when compared to that observed with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**. These differences in **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** and **Random-Dex-MSNs** *in vitro* efficacy agree with an enhanced **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** uptake mediated by the TNFR1 receptor in the cell membrane of pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages. Along the same lines, the efficacy of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** was evaluated in THP-1 monocytes. IL-1 β and TNF- α levels in stimulated THP-1 monocytes markedly diminished when treated with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanoparticles and remained unchanged using **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** (Figure S9). We also corroborated that **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, and free dexamethasone are unable to induce pro-inflammatory signalling and the associated cell death by pyroptosis by themselves (Figure 3C) reinforcing the biocompatibility of the nanomaterials (*vide ante*).

Finally, we studied in more detail the effect on the inflammasome pathway using **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**. Upon treatment with LPS and nigericin, caspase 1 is cleaved by the inflammasome and released to the media (Figure 3D and 3E), contributing to inflammatory signal spreading. Interestingly, treatment with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, and free dexamethasone, produces a significant reduction in active caspase-1 in the cell supernatants (Figure 3E). Despite caspase-1 is not a direct target of dexamethasone treatment, its reduction could be related to TNF- α and IL-1 β inhibition as this enzyme is involved in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and some of the responses of TNF- α are mediated by caspase-1 [63].

Figure 3. Analysis of inflammatory response in activated pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages in the presence of TNFR-Dex-MSNs. Macrophages (M1) were treated with **Random-Dex-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** (2 μ g/mL, equivalent to 1 μ M of dexamethasone), with free dexamethasone (1 μ M), and **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-RhB-MSNs** were used as a control (2 μ g/mL). A) IL-1 β and B) TNF- α cytokines levels from cell supernatants measured by ELISA. C) LDH release profile detected in cell supernatants as inflammatory cell death marker. D) Schematic representation of inflammasome activation pathway and the involved proteins. E) Western blot detection cleaved caspase-1 measured in cell supernatants and NLPR3, TNFR1, pro-Caspase 1, detected in cell lysates using GAPDH as reference protein.

Data represent the means \pm SEM of at least three independent experiments. Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA by comparing each group to pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages referred as M1 (** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$).

2.4. TNFR-Dex-MSNs exhibits greater therapeutic effect reducing acute lung injury.

Once confirmed the activity of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** *in vitro*, we moved one step forward and tested the therapeutic efficiency of the nanodevice in an acute lung injury inflammatory mice model. The ALI model was developed by the intratracheal administration of LPS (2.5 mg/kg in saline) to CD-1 mice for 24 h. **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** were intravenously administered by tail vein injection (25 mg/kg in PBS) to an equivalent dose of 10 mg/kg of free dexamethasone. Besides, **Random-Dex-MSNs** (25 mg/kg in PBS) was also used to determine the effect of the targeted delivery on the therapeutic effect. **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-RhB-MSNs** were also administered at 25 mg/kg as control in the presence and the absence of LPS. The inflammation in the ALI model for all groups was characterized by measuring the pro-inflammatory cytokines in bronchoalveolar fluid (BALF). Moreover, to determine the severity of lung injury, alterations in the alveolar-capillary barrier and histological evidence of tissue injury were also studied.

After LPS exposure, TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β were up-regulated in lungs as quantified in BALF by ELISA, thus evidencing the activation of a strong inflammatory response (Figures 4A, 4B and 4C). No significant differences were found in the levels of cytokines between the LPS group compared to LPS+**TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and LPS+**Random-RhB-MSNs**, discarding any additional effect of the nanoparticles in the inflammatory activation. This is correlated with the negligible inflammatory effect found in mice treated only with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** or **Random-RhB-MSNs** confirming the inability of the inorganic mesoporous scaffold to trigger any inflammatory adverse effect

and thus suggesting its biocompatibility. Besides, the levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β were significantly reduced in mice treated with LPS+**TNFR-Dex-MSNs** when compared to the LPS group (Figure 4A, 4B and 4C, light grey bars). On the other hand, slight differences in the therapeutic effect using **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** compared to **Dex** treatment were found, considering the high dose of the free drug used to treat this acute model of inflammation. Moreover, a higher efficacy in the reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokines was achieved in mice treated with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** when compared with those treated with **Random-Dex-MSNs**. These results are attributed to the enhanced **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** internalization, mediated by the TNFR1 receptor in pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages located in the inflamed lungs. The preferential and selective cargo delivery from TNFR-gated nanodevices was confirmed by targeting assays in the ALI mice model using **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-RhB-MSNs** after 24 h in the presence or absence of LPS treatment (Figure S10).

Figure 4. Evaluation of the therapeutic effect of TNFR-Dex-MSNs in LPS-ALI mice. The ALI model was performed after the LPS administration (2.5 mg/kg) to CD-1 mice for 24 h. Animals were treated by tail vein injection with dexamethasone (10 mg/kg), **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** and **Random-Dex-MSNs** (25 mg/kg in PBS; equivalent to 10 mg/kg of free dexamethasone) and with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-RhB-MSNs** (25 mg/kg in PBS) as control. Levels of A) IL-6, B) TNF- α and C) IL-1 β of pro-inflammatory cytokines in BALF measured by ELISA. The data represent the mean \pm SEM ($n \geq 6$) and statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA by comparing each group to LPS group (* $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$).

The severity of lung damage was studied by histology of lung tissues for all groups (Figure 5A). The most important hallmark of ALI is the diffuse alveolar damage in lung

tissue characterized by (i) neutrophil accumulation in vascular, interstitial, and alveolar spaces, (ii) the presence of hyaline membranes (proteins and dead cells) and other proteinaceous debris, and (iii) the interstitial thickening.[64,65] The healthy lung section was composed of thin alveolar walls (control in Figure 5A) whereas LPS treated mice presented serious tissue injury (LPS, LPS+**TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, LPS+**Random-RhB-MSNs** groups) distinguished by remarkable congestion and disruption of the alveolar architecture.[66] Despite the fact that certain alteration in the lung architecture was observed after the administration of **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-RhB-MSNs** (without LPS treatment), these changes were much less severe than those detected in LPS treated groups thus discarding serious lung damage by nanoparticles. Thus, although some studies reported a toxic role of the nanoparticles in the lungs, mainly associated with inhaled exposure [67] no significant signs of lung damage or toxicity were found after the treatment with the nanodevices. On the other hand, LPS+Dex, LPS+**TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, and LPS+**Random-Dex-MSNs** groups showed a remarkable attenuated lung injury. Thus, in mice treated with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, **Random-Dex-MSNs**, and dexamethasone the pulmonary architecture is almost similar to control groups, despite the impairment in the alveolar walls attributed to LPS instillation. These results were also assessed following a standard scoring system to determine the degree of acute lung injury referred to as ALI score (Figure 5B). ALI score (Table 5 in Supporting Information) was evaluated in different gradations of severity from the histological findings (neutrophils in the alveolar space, neutrophils in the interstitial space, hyaline membranes, proteinaceous debris filling the airspaces, and alveolar septal thickening).[65] ALI score for LPS groups (i.e. LPS, LPS+ **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, and LPS+ **Random-RhB-MSNs**) was in the 0.8-0.9 interval indicating a strong lung injury. Besides, mice treated with free dexamethasone, **Random-Dex-MSNs**, or **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** showed a marked reduction of the ALI score (with values of 0.43, 0.52 and 0.40, respectively) closer to the score of control groups, indicative of a noticeable decrease of lung injury.

Besides, lung sections were stained with specific markers to evaluate, in more detail, some of the histological findings determined in the ALI score. Myeloperoxidase (MPO) activity staining confirmed the accumulation of inflammatory cells (polymorphonuclear leukocyte type) in lungs in LPS treated mice, compared to LPS+**TNFR-Dex-MSNs** and LPS+Dex, in which MPO activity was reduced and therefore inflammation (Figure S11).[68] The Periodic Acid Schiff (PAS) marker was used to evaluate the alveolar proteinuria, characteristic in the exudative phase of acute lung injury, and was only observed in lung sections in LPS treated mice with desquamation to alveolar space (Figure S14).[69] Finally, changes in lung permeability were studied determining the total protein concentration in BALF. The accumulation of protein in BALF is correlated with the increase in vascular permeability induced by inflammation. Protein concentration in BALF drastically increased when LPS was administered (Figure 5), whereas levels of proteins decreased upon treatment with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, **Random-Dex-MSNs**, or dexamethasone. All these findings agree with the histology analysis of lung tissue images and ALI Score.

Figure 5. Evaluation of the therapeutic effect of TNFR-Dex-MSNs in lung tissue of LPS-ALI mice. The ALI model was performed after the LPS administration (2.5 mg/kg) to CD-1 mice for 24 h. Animals were treated by tail vein injection with dexamethasone (10 mg/kg), **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** and **Random-Dex-MSNs** (25 mg/kg in PBS; equivalent to 10 mg/kg of free dexamethasone) and with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **Random-RhB-**

MSNs (25 mg/kg in PBS) as control. A) Representative images of H&E stain of lung tissue with the different treatments. B) Histological assessment of the acute lung injury determined by ALI score. C) The total amount of protein in BALF, as lung permeability marker, measured by BCA assay. Data expressed as the mean \pm SEM (n=4) and statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA by comparing each group to the LPS group (****p<0.0001).

2.5. Targeted-lung delivery and reduction of adverse side effects derived from dexamethasone treatment using gated MSNs in the ALI mouse model

The results above suggest that TNFR-gated MSNs present a potential therapeutic effect to mitigate lung injury and could help to overcome the clinical limitations, related to derived side effects from therapy, through targeted delivery of therapeutics directly into the inflamed lungs. To further characterize the targeting effect of TNFR-gated nanodevices to inflamed lungs, we evaluated rhodamine B emission after 24 h of treatment with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** in the ALI mice model. The **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** nanoparticles were intravenously administered by tail vein injection (25 mg/kg in PBS), lungs were collected and visualized by fluorescence optical imaging using an IVIS Spectrum (Figure 6A). A remarkable fluorescent signal attributed to rhodamine B presence was registered in the case of inflamed lungs treated with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**. In contrast, lungs treated only with LPS or with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** alone showed negligible fluorescence. The rhodamine B emission was also quantified using the Living Image software (Figure 6B). As could be seen, the highest rhodamine B fluorescence was obtained for individuals treated with LPS+**TNFR-RhB-MSNs** when compared with the other conditions in which a weak fluorescence was detected. These results were corroborated by silicon biodistribution analysis in lungs and other selected organs (kidney, liver, spleen, tail) (Figure6C). A silicon pattern was clearly identified in individuals treated with nanoparticles compared to other groups. A preferential

accumulation of the nanoparticles in the lungs was also confirmed when compared with the spleen, liver, and kidney. The highest silicon content was detected in the lungs of individuals treated with LPS + **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** or LPS + **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** when compared with mice treated alone with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** group in which silicon was detected in less quantity. These results confirmed the targeting effect of TNFR-gated nanodevices with the subsequent cargo delivery only into the inflamed lungs in acute lung injury mice. Despite of the fact that final nanoparticles have a positive zeta potential value, the results suggested that the accumulation of the nanoparticles in lungs is mainly driven by the passive targeting effect (inflammation in lungs) and the active targeting effect through the TNFR peptide.

Figure 6. Evaluation of TNFR-RhB-MSNs in the inflamed lungs in an acute lung injury mice model. Animals were treated with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** (25 mg/kg in PBS) by tail vein injection in the absence or presence of LPS (2.5 mg/kg) for 24 h. A)

Representative lung images obtained using an IVIS spectrum equipment and B) quantification of rhodamine B associated fluorescence. Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA (* $p < 0.05$) (n=4). C) Biodistribution of the **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** and **TNFR-Dex-MNSs** silica scaffold in lung, liver, spleen, kidney, and tail. The graph exhibited the $\mu\text{g Si per g}$ of sample detected by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) in the indicated organs. The data represent the mean \pm SEM (n=5).

Regarding that a remarkable drawback of dexamethasone use is the high dosage needed to achieve the desired therapeutic effect in the site of action, different side adverse effects are developed in critical patients (*vide ante*). To mimic a more realistic scenario and evaluate the derived side effects of dexamethasone in clinic cases, high doses of the drug were used in this study. The progression of undesired effects from dexamethasone treatment (hyperglycemia, thrombosis, and systemic toxicity) were followed in mice treated with LPS+dexamethasone and compared with mice treated with LPS and **TNRF-Dex-MSNs**. Hyperglycaemia is caused as a result of an increase in glucose levels since glucocorticoids stimulate gluconeogenesis [70,71]. Figure 7A shows that although glucose levels were altered in mice treated with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** and free dexamethasone, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** administration induced a noticeable reduction (ca. 1.7-fold) in the concentration of the free monosaccharide when compared to that found when free dexamethasone was used. Some studies have demonstrated that the use of glucocorticoids increases the risk of thrombosis because glucocorticoids promote the synthesis of different factors involved in coagulation [72]. To evaluate the risk of thrombosis associated with the use of dexamethasone and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** platelet levels were evaluated. The obtained results are depicted in Figure 7B. As could be seen, a marked increase in the platelet levels was observed for the treatment with

free dexamethasone, whereas mice treated with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** presented platelet levels in the normal range for healthy individuals.

Additionally, the inflammatory response, by measuring cells of the white series (leukocytes, neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes) at lungs (BALF) (Figure 7C) and systemic level (Figures 7D, 7E, and 7F) was assessed. Figure 7D shows that levels of neutrophils at systemic levels for individuals instilled with LPS, and treated with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs**, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, and free dexamethasone, are in the expected range for individuals that present an acute inflammatory response (neutrophils > 40% and lymphocytes < 60%). However, in the case of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**, the number of neutrophils is lower and the lymphocytes population at the systemic level is much closer to the health conditions when compared to other groups. These results agree with the marked reduction in the total amount of leukocytes (5.5-fold) observed in BALF of **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** treated mice, compared to LPS-treated mice or with free dexamethasone-treated group with a smaller reduction (3.5-fold), pointing out to a higher therapeutic outcome using the TNFR-nanodevice. In accordance, a major misbalance in the leukocyte population at the systemic level was observed in the group treated with free dexamethasone (neutrophils ca. 85% and lymphocytes ca. 15%).

Figure 7. Evaluation of the impact of encapsulation on dexamethasone derived side-effects. The ALI model was performed after the LPS administration (2.5 mg/kg) to CD-1 mice for 24 h. The data showed groups of animals treated by tail vein injection with dexamethasone (10 mg/kg) and **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** (25 mg/kg in PBS; equivalent to 10 mg/kg of free dexamethasone). **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** were used as control (25 mg/kg in PBS). A) Hyperglycemia evaluation by measuring glucose levels. B) Thrombosis effect determined by platelet levels. The data represent the mean \pm SEM (n=6) and statistical significance was determined using Student's t-test ($P < 0.05$). C) Leukocytes account in BALF as an indicator of inflammation focus. D, E) and F) Percentage of neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes as systemic inflammation

indicators. The dashed lines indicate the values for healthy individuals. The data represent the mean \pm SEM (n=6) and statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA by comparing each group to the LPS group (*p<0.01; **p<0.05; ***p<0.001).

All these results evidence that encapsulation of dexamethasone into **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** allows to achieve a high therapeutic outcome while attenuating some of the undesired side effects related to the use of free drug due to its systemic and unspecific biodistribution. Moreover, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** improve dexamethasone solubility and protect the drug until the nanoparticle reaches the target site, thus enhancing drug bioavailability. Regarding safety issues related to the use of silica nanomaterials for lung delivery, the careful design of the nanoparticles as well as the selection of a proper dose and exposure can help to limit their possible lung toxicity. Besides, *in vivo* research using MSNs has increased in the last years the knowledge about the biocompatibility, degradability, and clearance of these materials which corroborated that MSNs can be degraded and therefore excreted from the body.[13,73] The MSNs are constituted by -Si-O- bonds which are easily hydrolysed generating orthosilicic acid (Si(OH)₄), which is well-tolerated by the body and finally excreted, being this an indication that MSNs do not accumulate.[74] In the body MSNs can be processed by the reticuloendothelial system (RES) (monocytes, macrophages, cell from liver, etc.) or in the diseased target (such as tumours or inflamed tissues) into small fragments or constitutes, and then return to blood circulation to finally be removed. Different studies established renal clearance as the main excretion way of MSNs followed, in a lower proportion, by the hepatobiliary way, being MSNs efficiently removed from the body regardless of the route of administration, dose, shape, size, and surface features, generally after a few days or weeks.[75,76]

3. CONCLUSIONS

A nanodevice based on mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with dexamethasone and capped with a peptide targeting the TNFR1 receptor (**TNFR-Dex-MSNs**) is prepared and characterized. Our results demonstrate that TNFR-gated nanodevices are preferentially internalized by pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages, which overexpressed the TNFR1 receptor, and are able to release the cargo after the enzymatic hydrolysis of the capping peptide. Besides, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanoparticles reduce cytokine levels *in vitro* in activated pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages and *in vivo* in an ALI mice model. Reduction of inflammation and attenuation of lung injuries with **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** nanoparticles is assessed also by histopathological studies.

Moreover, **TNFR-Dex-MSNs** exhibit a greater therapeutic effect leading to the inflammatory response in inflamed lungs with lower adverse side effects compared to free dexamethasone. This is attributed to the preferential accumulation of TNFR-gated nanomaterials in the inflamed lungs. Targeting of the nanoparticles is confirmed by IVIS analysis using **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** as well as by silicon biodistribution studies in mice treated with **TNFR-RhB-MSNs** or **TNFR-Dex-MSNs**. Our findings also suggested that the gated nanodevices do not provide any adverse side effects or lung damage, pointing to their potential suitability for clinical application, although more research efforts are needed to address the safety of these nanomaterials in clinics.

Based on the above, we demonstrate that targeted-delivery of glucocorticoids using gated-mesoporous silica nanoparticles is an attractive tool for direct and specific drug release to inflamed lungs in ALI by taking advantage of the passive and active targeting provided by engineered MSNs while reducing undesired drug side effects. These results might find application in the treatment of other devastating lung diseases such as Chronic Pulmonary Obstructive Disease (COPD), asthma, pulmonary fibrosis, respiratory infectious diseases, and the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, in which lung injury has a critical role. Based on this, dexamethasone was the first drug to show

some life-saving efficacy in COVID-19 patients and some authors have already pointed the potential of using nanomedicines for enhancing drug availability and drug efficacy for improving COVID-19 management.[77] The intrinsic properties of MSNs can provide unique advantages for fighting inflammation and infections in the lungs through the on-command drug delivery, by targeting macrophages as we have demonstrated, or by recruiting immune cells or acting as adjuvants. Considering the urgent need for treatments for the devastating lung diseases, we hope that these results encourage the development of new MSNs based systems for pulmonary delivery.

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